

S1. The phonon dispersion of graphene

S1.1 The relationship between real and reciprocal lattice space

Figure S1. The diagrams of real and reciprocal lattices for graphene: (a) the structures of the primitive cell (the low left corner) and the supercell cell by $N \times N$ primitive cells; (b) the reciprocal lattice primitive cell with $N \times N$ k -mesh grid and high-symmetry k -point paths; (c) the relationship between primitive cells in the real and reciprocal spaces. The green open circles in (b) and (c) are the high-symmetry points in the Brillouin zone. The supercell cell by $N \times N$ primitive cells shown in (a) was transformed into the $N \times N$ k -mesh grid shown in (b) by Fourier projection method according to solid-state physics. N is the number of primitive cells along the directions of the primitive vectors in computing cell, and N is equal to 13 in (a) and (b) for clarity.

S1.2 The phonon dispersion of graphene

Figure S2. The phonon dispersion curves for hexagonal graphene at 300K calculated by Fourier projection method from the trajectories simulated by molecular dynamics (left) and first-principles molecular dynamics (right). The black points are the peak positions of phonon spectra. Red curves are guides to the eye.

S2. The phonon dispersion of BCC-Fe obtained by Fourier projection method

S2.1 The relationship between real and reciprocal lattice space of BCC lattice

Figure S3. The conventional lattice, primitive cell, reciprocal lattice primitive cell for (a) BCC lattice. (b) is the conventional first Brillouin zone of the BCC lattice [55]. The black dots and lines in (a) constitute the conventional lattice, with the blue representing the primitive cell and the red representing the reciprocal lattice primitive cell. The green points are the high-symmetry points in reciprocal lattice primitive cell; yellow lines are the k -point paths; green dashed lines are the body diagonal of reciprocal lattice.

S2.2 The phonon dispersion of BCC-Fe

Figure S4. The phonon dispersion curves of BCC-Fe at 300K calculated by Fourier projection method from the MD trajectories. The black points are the peak positions of phonon spectra. Red curves are guides to the eye.

S3. The phonon dispersion of FCC-Cu obtained by Fourier projection method

S3.1 The relationship between real and reciprocal lattice space of FCC lattice

Figure S5. The conventional lattice, primitive cell, reciprocal lattice primitive cell for (a) FCC lattice. (b) is the conventional first Brillouin zone of FCC lattice. The black dots and lines in (a) constitute the conventional lattice, with the blue representing the primitive cell and the red representing the reciprocal lattice primitive cell. The green points are the high-symmetry points in reciprocal lattice primitive cell; yellow lines are the k -point paths; green and purple dashed lines are the body and face diagonal of reciprocal lattice, respectively.

S3.2 The phonon dispersion of FCC-Cu

Figure S6. The phonon dispersion curves of FCC-Cu at 300K calculated by Fourier projection method from the MD trajectories. The black points are the peak positions of phonon spectra. Red curves are guides to the eye.